

OPEN EARTH MONITOR

D2.5 Feasibility and Impact Assessment

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List of Acronyms

OEMC	Open Earth Monitor Cyberinfrastructure
IFGI	Institute for Geoinformatics, University of Münster
WP	Working Package
EO	Earth Observation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
LP	Leading Partner
OGH	Open Geo Hub
GFZ	Helmholtz German Research Centre for Geosciences
WU	Wageningen University
MPG	Max-Planck-Gesellschaft zur Förderung der Wissenschaften e.V.
EURAC	EURAC Research
CNR	National Research Council of Italy
GILAB	GiLab DOO Belgrade
LWE	LifeWatch ERIC
ETH	Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich
IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
HE	Horizon Europe
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNCCD	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification
UNCBD	United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
D2.1	Deliverable 2.1 - Stakeholder Committee and "Open-Earth-Monitor design" Workshop

Executive summary

The first part of this report presents the feasibility analysis of the important and critical stakeholder needs identified by the use-cases (32). For each of the requirements, the report shows its implementation risks, potential obstacles, and mitigation strategies. This information is grouped per use-case and shown in a comprehensive table in Appendix A, whereas the summary of the feasibility analysis is presented in the first section of the report. For the reader's convenience, we also provide the link to the online version of the feasibility table.

The second part of the report presents the impact assessment of the use cases as well as general- and use-case-level measures to monitor and assess the impact of the tools and data that will be developed within the OEMC use-cases. The impact assessment and measures are largely based on an analysis of the interviews carried out with the use-case-related stakeholders. The last section of the report reflects on use-case diversity and project feasibility, and discusses potential synergies with other projects and initiatives.

The feasibility assessment shows that most of the work and tasks in this project are feasible or very feasible, and only a small fraction of tasks pose serious challenges. In many cases, the challenges are related to external factors which are beyond the control of this project (e.g., data access and longer-term time series of data availability). Risks and potential implications for the project will be continuously tracked and documented. Potential mitigation measures to reduce the different risks have been carefully defined and can be implemented if needed.

A broader general risk of the project is that, with 32 use-cases, significant effort will take place across different fields and the innovation will be incremental. Such an approach has pros and cons. The advantage is that generally the risks are reduced, as the shortcomings of one or a few use-cases will not jeopardize the overall project, and the overall impact will still be relatively high. The downside of this approach is that due to the high number use-cases, the impact of the use-cases will be incremental rather than lead to a step change. Nevertheless, past experience has shown that those step changes are still possible even when few resources can be allocated.

Disclaimer: Please NOTE that the information provided in the report does not reflect the view of organizations, but of interviewed individuals.

Stakeholders' Needs and Feasibility

The OEMC design workshop (D2.1), which took place at the project kick-off meeting in Wageningen, put use cases at the center of the OEMC project. Since then, 32 OEMC use cases were established, each with at least one stakeholder directly influencing the design and results (tools and data) developed by the use case. In addition to identifying and establishing different stakeholder groups (D2.1), WP2 designed and carried out a survey with the use-case-related stakeholders to understand their needs, i.e., requirements, for the use cases they are involved in. At our internal project meeting at IFGI on 15-17 May in Münster, Germany, WP2 organized a workshop in which each use-case leader was asked to identify and present the most challenging stakeholder requirements. This workshop and the follow-up discussions on feasibility, risk, and mitigation strategies for the stakeholder requirements were the basis for the feasibility study presented in this report.

The interview process with use-case-related stakeholders is ongoing, but at least one interview has already been completed for most of the use cases (29 out of 32). Thus, we present here the feasibility only for use cases with at least one completed stakeholder interview. As the diversity of technical, data, and methodological use case aspects is high, we rely on the use case leaders who identified the most important and most critical stakeholder requirements and commented on their (a) feasibility, (b) potential obstacles, i.e., risks, and (c) mitigation strategies, i.e., alternative solutions. In total, 116 stakeholder requirements were identified. The feasibility for each stakeholder requirement was scored according to risk levels presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Feasibility risk levels assigned to the stakeholder requirements.

RISK LEVELS	PERCENTAGE [%]
Very Feasible	81 – 100
Feasible	61 – 80
Less Feasible	41 – 60
Not Feasible	21 – 40
Very Inappropriate	0 – 20

For a better understanding and presentation, we categorized the identified obstacles into the following 10 types. (1) **Capacity Constraints** refer to the requirements requiring more time, personnel, or processing costs; (2) **Data Harmonisation** is where the requirement is to combine different data sources; (3) **Data Volume** refers to requirements demanding a large volume of data to be stored, processed, or analyzed; (4) **Definitions** refers to obstacles where the terminology, the definition of variables, or final product is unclear; (5) **EO Data** referring to the requirements where EO data over a larger temporal period or higher spatial resolution are missing; Similarly, (6) **In-Situ Data** refers to the requirements where more in-situ data or larger spatial coverage of in-situ data is missing; (7) **Methodological** obstacles refers to requirements that need some methodological development to process EO data to the required products;

(8) **Processing Infrastructure** refers to the requirements that demand large processing infrastructure, or the cases where it is not clear where and how the data processing will be performed; (9) **Technical** refers to the requirements that require additional technical solutions for data accessing or presenting, lack of internet connection, or connection with other platforms and systems; Finally, (10) **N/A** is used when the obstacle is not provided.

We have presented the stakeholder requirements in an extensive table, showing each requirement in a separate row and, with its feasibility score, listed its obstacles, alternative solutions or mitigation strategies, and its obstacle type given as separate columns (see Appendix A, Table 2). As the table is comprehensive and covers 18 pages, we provide here [a link to the online version of the table](#) for the convenience of the reader. The stakeholder requirements are further grouped per use case, and for use cases with missing requirements, we reported about their current status. Based on the information contained in the table, our feasibility assessment shows that three-quarters of the stakeholder requirements are seen by use case leaders as feasible and very feasible (Figure 1). On the other hand, most of the obstacles (>60%) are either methodological, EO data- or in-situ data-driven (Figure 2). Alternative solutions or mitigation strategies are given for each obstacle in Table 2.

Figure 1: Distribution of the feasibility scores across the stakeholder requirements.

Figure 2: Distribution of the obstacle types across the stakeholder requirements.

Impact Assessment

We are doing an ex-ante impact assessment to anticipate in what aspects the likely impact of the project will be. We have also revisited the KPIs as they provide a good indication and measurable criteria of impact. The impact takes place in an innovation HE projects such as this one, both on the novelty side by the dissemination of new data, methods, and tools, as well as on the policy side. Nevertheless, it has to be stressed upfront that the impact on decision making of an innovation project will always be limited since it pushes technology readiness level further but does not claim to provide an operationally sustainable system. Therefore, it is important that indirect impacts of the project, such as those related to policies, are gathered and documented and the appropriate measures are defined. Another aspect which OEMC is very keen to influence and impact are international initiatives and conventions such as the UNFCCC, UNCCD as well as UNCBD. Some work in particular on biodiversity will also provide potential inputs to IPBES and the conservation community. The work undertaken does not intend to replace existing monitoring and global assessment tools such as Global Forest, Global Resource watch, or Trends.Earth in the field of land degradation neutrality. It rather complements existing, established monitoring systems and provides potentially new insights. The path to impact is generally by either providing better and improved data or tools which impact the overall information base for decision and policy making as well as benchmarking (e.g., monitoring change). This incremental improvement in the information base will lead to better decisions, based on a richer set of tools and data.

Figure 3: Word cloud generated from the EU policies, strategies, directives, and regulations that are identified to be related to the OEMC use cases. The size of the words corresponds to the number of the OEMC use cases related to.

As an overview of EU policies, strategies, and regulations related to OEMC use cases, we present them here as a word cloud inside the outer shape of the European countries (Figure 3). Please note that the

locations and orientations of particular EU policies, strategies, and regulations are random, i.e., they are not referring to the particular EU region or country but rather relevant at the EU and European levels. We only counted how many times particular policies are mentioned in the stakeholder interviews or recognized by WP2 as related to the use case. According to this number, we rendered the size of a particular policy in the word cloud.

Figure 4: OEMC use case global footprint at the country level. The darker the color the more use cases are related to the country. Please note that OEMC use cases providing global data are not plotted for a better overview.

We also visualized countries on a World map to present what is the global footprint of OEMC use cases (Figure 4). The countries are highlighted according to the number of use cases that will have products covering (partly or fully) their territory. As we have many use cases providing EU-wide products, for the sake of map clarity, we decided to count them only once and additionally only highlight those that will have small-scale OEMC products within their territory or from where an OEMC consortium partner is coming. The OEMC use cases providing global products are not plotted for better map clarity. Nevertheless, we included Indonesia, for example, because OEMC has a use case that will monitor global mangrove soil carbon and this country has by far the largest mangrove cover among other countries in the World. Furthermore, this also helped to emphasize the pan-tropical impact of the OEMC use cases. Nevertheless, we are aware that this first version of the OEMC global footprint map still has room for further improvements, particularly by introducing better categorization and visualizations of different impact types, which due to time constraints, remains the subject for future work.

Table 3 in Appendix B introduces the results of the interviewed stakeholders for each use case respectively in regards to any European or national regulations or directives and other policies which might possibly benefit from the OEMC use-cases.

During the interviews, stakeholders were asked to list any policies, directives or regulations that they think might possibly benefit from their use-case. Accordingly, these results are listed in black color in Table 3. Where input from stakeholders was missing or the information was considered insufficient, we carried out further analysis. Based on the provided description of the use-cases, the entire interviews, and our own additional research, each use-case in the table was complimented with further names of policies and

directives which we anticipate might benefit from it. This added information is introduced in blue and orange in Table 3 as well.

Through further analysis, we attempted to categorize the impact type for each use-case according to the interviews and the use-case general expectations and description. As follows, we introduce two levels of impact types: a primary level of impact and a secondary level. Figure 5 summarizes those impact types for the OEMC use cases.

Within the primary level impact, the following five impact categories have been established: (i) impact policy, (ii) improving data and information, (iii) improving stakeholder tools, (iv) data processing and (v) tool & data creation. With the secondary level impact the following impact categories were identified: (i) impact policy, (ii) improving data and information, (iii) data processing and (iv) tool & data creation and (v) no secondary impact.

Figure 5: Frequency of suggested impact types (right) and of second suggested impact types (left), for all use cases.

Categorizing use-case impact serves to capture the heterogeneity of the use-cases, toward a similarly heterogenous measure of impact. The benefit of this is to evaluate impact as precisely as possible. For example, all use cases would eventually have policy direct or indirect impact, though some of them are being constructed specifically with this purpose (i.e., following guidelines determined in policy for monitoring, or providing inputs that are thought to feedback an established policy process). Therefore, it would be unfair to some projects to evaluate impact only in terms of policy, as this was not the original (primary) objective, or a policy may still not be as clearly identified or existing.

Two challenges arose while defining impact categories. First, their creation is highly subjective, and it depends on which factor of the use-case the reader is focusing on while assessing its possible impact, which depends on many other factors, such as previous knowledge and experience of the use-case. Second, the impact types are not binary, well-defined categories, but are fuzzy distinctions, which may overlap to some degree. **The most important criteria to be considered for version 2 of this document is that every use-case representative and stakeholders sees their possible impact reflected clearly in one of these categories.**

Contributing to Data Gap-Filling

As analyzed in the previous section of impact types, almost two thirds of the use-cases were categorized under the impact type “tool & data creation”. As follows, most use-cases or stakeholders pointed to some sort of data gap to be filled by the creation of new data (i.e., maps with innovative variables or resolution) or tools (i.e., making available condensed information for decision making).

At the general level, it is clear that an impact of the project will be related in some measure to bridging these data gaps. For this reason, it is important to make these transparent, as reported in the interviews by stakeholders, in Table 4 of Appendix C. One challenge identified is the heterogeneity in precision and in the nature of these data gaps' descriptions, making them hard to categorize. For this reason, **it is recommended that the table be revised by the use-case representatives and stakeholders, so they can agree on which specific data gaps will be addressed in the project, and these can then be inserted as measures of impact for the version 2 of this document.**

Measures for Impact Assessment

We introduce two levels of impact assessment: (a) project-level and (b) use-case-level impact. Accordingly, below we suggest measures for those two levels. Due to the diversity of the OEMC use-cases and the complexity of measuring impact, **we propose reviewing aspects of these measures at a further stage in version 2 of this report, after additional consultations with the use-case leaders and stakeholders.**

Project-level measures aim to quantitatively assess and monitor the general impact of the project, and will include the following measures:

- o Number of FAIR and open data sets PRODUCED by the OEMC project.
- o Number of FAIR and open data sets IMPROVED by the OEMC project.
- o Number of reproducible open tools/workflows PRODUCED by the OEMC project.
- o Number of reproducible open tools/workflows IMPROVED by the OEMC project.
- o Number of OEMC-related publications.
- o Number of use-cases which enhance the data and information base for a specific EU policy.
- o Number of EU, national, and international organizations interested in using OEMC tools and data.

Use-case-level measures aim to assess and monitor the impact of individual use cases. As the diversity of use cases is high in several aspects (output, spatial coverage, provided service, etc.), it is difficult to introduce measures that suit all use cases. Therefore, **we will carry out another round of stakeholder interviews (towards the end of the project) exploring the impact of the use case.** The interviews will have questions targeting different impact types such as policy impact, data impact, and tools (workflows) impact. Below are examples of such questions for each impact type:

- o Policy impact:
 - Have the use-case results contributed to improved decision-making?
 - Has OEMC contributed to improving / designing /monitoring policies?
- o Data impact:
 - How many people are using use-case data in your organization?
 - How many new people learned about the new/improved data sets as a result of the project?
 - How many organizations frequently use OEMC based data?
 - How many downloads of published, open data sets took place throughout the project?
- o Tools and workflows impact:
 - Is the use-case solution used in your work?

- Did the use-case solution work as expected, or have the impact expected?
- Has the use-case tool replaced your existing workflow?
- Has the project helped to develop new official operational data streams?
- o Sustainability aspect:
 - How will the data and tools be used after the project?
 - How could the data or tools be improved?

It should be noted that WP2 will be continuously engaging with stakeholders, particularly at the OEMC related events such as the Global Workshop 2023 planned for later this year, as well as the following ones. Those occasions will be leveraged to hear and collect feedback, for example, from the Stakeholder Committee, about project-level measures, and from use-case-related stakeholders and use-case leaders about the use-case-level measures and questions. This feedback will be used to refine the above and introduce new measures and questions.

Discussion and Outlook

The feasibility assessment, which took place as part of the questionnaire and was then graphically summarized, shows that most of the work and tasks in this project are **very feasible or feasible** and only a small fraction of tasks pose serious challenges. In many cases, the challenges are related to external factors which are beyond the control of this project (e.g., data access and longer-term time series of data availability).

As outlined already in the proposal, risks and potential implications for the project will be continuously tracked and documented. Potential mitigation measures to reduce the different risks have been carefully defined and can be implemented if needed.

A broader general risk of the project is that, with **32 use cases**, a lot of effort will take place across different fields and the innovation will be incremental. Such an approach has pros and cons. The advantage is that generally the risks are reduced, as the shortcomings of one or a few use cases will not jeopardize the overall project, and the overall impact will still be relatively high. The downside of this approach is that due to the many use-cases the impact will only happen in each of the use-cases and be incremental rather than lead to a step change. Had resources been more bundled such a step change would be more likely. Nevertheless, past experience has shown that those step changes are still possible even when few resources can be allocated.

Another aspect of the project is the complementarity to existing initiatives. As already stressed the project aims to enhance and complement existing initiatives based on the extensive work which has already been done in identifying those important global initiatives such as Global Forest Watch, Global Resource Watch, Trends.Earth and the different existing monitoring initiatives globally and European-wide as well as those which are national and local. For example, a new watch family namely Global Pasture Watch has been created and the OEMC complements this initiative, which is partly led by members of this consortium, meaning the contribution will be the enhancement of an existing system, or one that is currently being built.

One important aspect already touched upon before is the level of ambition an HE innovation action can have. The actual impact on direct decision-making will always be to some degree limited as decision-makers will have to rely on long-term functioning sustainable operational systems. Decision-makers tend not to like to rely on data streams which cannot be guaranteed in the long term and are project bound. Therefore, we also propose **to measure more indirect impacts and incremental**

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improvements, and we propose sustainability measures for the project to evaluate which components and use-cases are likely to exist beyond the project.

In version II of this document, we also plan to provide more concrete detail on which tools and data will be made openly available and will become part of a longer-term open data ecosystem.

Appendix A – Feasibility Assessment Table

Table 2: The extensive table with the stakeholder requirements and their risk assessment. LP org is the leading partner organization. The online version of the table can be found on the following [LINK](#).

Use Case Number	Title	LP org	Requirements	Feasibility	Obstacles	Solutions	Obstacle type
1	Land Degradation Neutrality tool	OGH	National degradation self-determination , solutions & monitoring	Feasible	Very open brief. Requires further discussion.	TBD	Definitions
			30 m land cover 2000-2022+	Feasible	Data volume, possibly redundant by other efforts?	Global automated EML	Data Volume
			30m SOC mapping 2000-2022+	Very Feasible	Data volume, various point licensing	EML + automated point licensing tools	Data Volume
			LPD re-mapping 2000-2022+, including land potential and resilience	Feasible	Clarity over why existing predictions differ so much	Provide guidance on selection of dataset based on which type of ecosystem to be analysed, provide land potential and resilience metrics	Methodological
			Participatory re-mapping	Very Feasible	Scaleup may be expensive	User annotated training points &/or areas	Capacity Constraints
2	EU soil observatory farmer alert system	OGH	Bare earth spectra for EU	Feasible	Large data quantities / missing values	Existing algorithms work	Methodological
			Soil erosion / soil salinization directly from EO data	Less Feasible	Missing training points for longer time-spans	Requires testing	Methodological
			SOC changes	Feasible	Missing bulk density	Will be implemented in the project	In-Situ Data
			Maps of biological indicators	Not Feasible	Missing training data with e.g. worm density	Requires testing	In-Situ Data

3	Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tool	OGH	Spatial resolution (250mx250m, ideally 10m x 10m)	Feasible	No long enough time series of 10mx10m available	Integrating Sentinel in the time series for recent years	EO Data
			Temporal resolution: 2000 - 2022+, annually (ideally monthly)	Feasible	Monthly: a lot of storage	Need to find solutions for big data storage in general	Data Volume
			Option to choose between different legislations to display data options	Less Feasible	Legislations change over time, needs continuous updating after end of project, which legislations should be available to begin with	Allow combination of different data sets, that will be aggregated in the report, but user would have to choose the data sets	Definitions
			Local data to improve estimates	Feasible	Local data will be in various types of formats and of origin	Limit addition of local data to specific types of data that can be added / they need to be uploaded in a pre-defined format	In-Situ Data
			Future projections (desired, but not required)	Less Feasible	May go beyond available time-resources to compute for each indicator	Focus on only few indicators (e.g. FAPAR)	Capacity Constraints
4	Mosquito alert system for Italy (zanzara tigre)	OGH	Distribution in areas not covered by the current monitoring system	Very Feasible	Absent	N/A	N/A
			Increase accuracy of current interpolation methods	Very Feasible	Our solution may prove to be in the worst case scenario as accurate as the current one	N/A	Methodological
			Inclusion of predictor variables and explainability of the results	Less Feasible	Using many predictor variables may make things difficult	Use a hybrid-approach: machine learning models that are based on known driving factors	Methodological
			Scenario forecasting tools	Feasible	Model needs to be trained only on variables that have robust future projections estimates	Limit the model to those known variables which can be accurately forecast (temperature, precipitation ecc)	Methodological
5	Forest management & tracking tool for Croatia	OGH	Env data for Croatia / forests integrated and analysis-ready	Very Feasible	Lack of internet connection inside of the park	Solution with support offline support and data synchronization	Technical
			Objective framework to assess forest dynamics	Very Feasible	Lack of harmonized and organized ground data	Match the historical forest management events in the park with EO data of last decades	Data Harmonisation

			Economic assessment of ecosystem forest services	Feasible	Spatial mapping of ecosystem forest services	Partnership local researchers focused in this subject	Methodological
6	Soil carbon accounting system for world mangroves	OGH	Stakeholder is missing				
7	EU construction tracking system in forests	terra signa	Forest footprint map	Very Feasible	N/A	N/A	N/A
			Forest density map	Feasible	access to in-situ data	Stakeholders provide access to in-situ data, or we use available open in-situ or citizen-science data	In-Situ Data
			Forest volume map	Feasible	access to in-situ data	Stakeholders provide access to in-situ data, or we use available open in-situ or citizen-science data	In-Situ Data
			Forest basal area map	Feasible	access to in-situ data	Stakeholders provide access to in-situ data, or we use available open in-situ or citizen-science data	In-Situ Data
			Map of construction based disturbance	Very Feasible	N/A	N/A	N/A
			Map of forest loss due to construction	Feasible	access to in-situ data	Stakeholders provide access to in-situ data, or we use available open in-situ or citizen-science data	In-Situ Data
8	Global monitoring system for livestock and grasslands / pastures	OGH	30-m global annual maps for pasture areas	Feasible	Access to GLAD Landsat ARD-2 (1.3 PB)	Shipping hard drives to Europe	EO Data
			10-m annual maps for pasture areas of Brazil	Less Feasible	Processing platform for ARCO Sentinel data cubes	Use OpenEO Cloud platform or OGH computing infrastructure	Processing Infrastructure
			Mapping degraded and not-degraded lands	Less Feasible	Objectively define land degradation and quantify it through EO data	Frequent feedback from stakeholder to guide the development of the dashboard	Definitions

9	Crop yield monitoring system for Africa	OGH	Training samples for crop types	Very Feasible	Lack of consistent and harmonized training samples for crop types in the pilot areas	Data-sharing agreement with IITA for accessing local data + MLHub data compilation	In-Situ Data
			10—5m annual country-level maps	Feasible	Processing platform for ARCO Sentinel data cubes	Use OpenEO Cloud platform or OGH computing infrastructure	Processing Infrastructure
			Training samples for crop yield	Less Feasible	Lack of consistent and harmonized training samples for crop yield in the pilot areas	Partnership with other local organizations or changing the methodology (empirical / mechanistic model)	In-Situ Data
10	Large-area estimation of forest carbon emissions	GFZ	AGB map	Feasible	In-situ data not available in certain parts of the world	Integration of ground and satellite data (removing errors)	In-Situ Data
			AGB change	Feasible	Quality of the AGB map and validation results (quality tbd given validation results). EO Data and long-time series data availability, ground data with limited coverage	Availability of ground reference data for change, integration of ground and satellite data (removing errors)	EO Data
			Carbon stock map	Feasible	Quality of the AGB map and validation results, EO Data and long-time series data availability	Integration of ground and satellite data (removing errors)	EO Data
			Carbon stock changes	Feasible	Quality of the AGB map, AGB change, and validation results (quality tbd given validation results). Reference data not available in certain parts of the world	Availability of ground reference data for change, integration of ground and satellite data (removing errors)	In-Situ Data
11	EU-rapid forest disturbance monitoring tool	WU	Tool must be run on the European cloud platform	Feasible	Readiness and accessibility of the cloud platform to run on near-real time.	N/A	Processing Infrastructure

			Product assessed using independent reference	Feasible	Availability of reference data	Citizen science initiative (IIASA) to collect reference data at EU scale. Link with HEurope Forwards project, which collects large amount of training/validation data	In-Situ Data
			Highly accurate detection	Feasible	Low sensitivity of C-band Radar	Utilizing dense C-band time series and forthcoming L-band radar missions	EO Data
12	Tropical deforestation monitoring and characterisation tool	WU	Results developed in OEMC should run on the Brazil Data Cube	Feasible	Real time access to SAR data to run in Brazil Data Cube	A near real time cloud service to access data to run in Brazil Data Cube	Processing Infrastructure
			Improved deforestation alerts and drivers of land use change	Very Feasible	N/A	N/A	Methodological
			National (Brazil) / Pan-tropical product on deforestation alerts and drivers	Feasible	Detecting alerts in pantropical dry forests	Train a deep neural network algorithm to provide alerts in pantropical dry forest.	Methodological
			Highly accurate detection	Feasible	Low sensitivity of C-band Radar	Utilizing dense C-band time series and forthcoming L-band radar missions	EO Data
13	Tool to estimate local temperatures changes following an increase in forest cover	MPG	Tackle daily cycle	Feasible	can only use geostationary satellites (not tested before)	Use SEVIRI data (geostationary)	Methodological
			repeat for every year within 2015-2022+	Feasible	more data processing than expected	Try first some years and then expand as feasible	Processing Infrastructure
			use tree species maps instead of broad PFTs	Feasible	input data quality is not so readily available and may require adjustments	use maps from EFI	EO Data
			Extend from Europe to Africa	Less Feasible	More processing required. Not same data quality (e.g. species specific maps)	use tree density from U. Copenhagen	Processing Infrastructure

			Applicable on their platform: BDAP	Feasible	Dependency on JRC	Work with JRC	Technical
			Should integrate in other EU forest observatory	Feasible	Dependency on JRC	Work with JRC	Technical
14	Planet health index	MPG	To be able to analyse impact of climate or biosphere on socio-economic activities (or vice-versa)	Feasible	Need to summarize many different datasets into lower number of dimensions	Adopt 3 axis approach (atmosphere, biosphere, anthroposphere)	Methodological
			Main components should be interpretable	Feasible	Many input variables can be correlated	Use canonical correlation analysis (CCA) to explain one data sphere with another (and vice-versa)	Methodological
			Applicable to future scenarios	Not Feasible	Data of different quality between present and future (e.g. no EO for future) and would require harmonisation	Leave this for future developments	Methodological
			Be able to study effects of biodiversity	Less Feasible	Global gridded data on biodiversity in time not readily available	Concentrate first on more general biosphere variables	EO Data
15	SIF-based high spatial resolution GPP flux estimations	MPG	Product should provide spatio-temp. variations of terrestrial GPP	Feasible	Need to convert SIF to GPP	Calibrate with eddy covariance flux towers	Methodological
			Resolve fine details such as coastlines and islands	Feasible	SIF is coarse resolution (at best 5 km)	Spatial downscaling should be applied (here based on hybrid AI)	Methodological
			Sensitivity to fine scale changes (forest disturbances, crop dynamics, etc)	Less Feasible	Requires fine temporal and spatial resolution (possibly finer than what can be downscaled)	Test the use of Sentinel 2 data in the downscaling	Methodological

			Longer archive	Not Feasible	Sentinel 5P data only available since 2018	Reconstruct archive from other coarser SIF instruments	EO Data
16	High resolution SWE in selected mountain regions	EURAC	Spatial coverage for South Tyrol Catchments	Very Feasible	Availability of ground truth data.	Evaluate the performance of the method where possible. Then decide to which degree extrapolations can be made, or which accuracy measures suit extrapolations.	In-Situ Data
			Spatial Coverage for selected regions	Feasible	Availability of ground truth data.	Evaluate the performance of the method where possible. Then decide to which degree extrapolations can be made, or which accuracy measures suit extrapolations.	In-Situ Data
			Spatial coverage for whole Alps	Less Feasible	Availability of ground truth data.	Evaluate the performance of the method where possible. Then decide to which degree extrapolations can be made, or which accuracy measures suit extrapolations.	In-Situ Data
			Temporal Coverage over the last 5-6 years	Very Feasible	Availability of Sentinel Data	More than 5-6 years cannot be produced due to unavailability of Sentinel Mission Data.	EO Data
			Temporal Coverage over the last 30 years	Not Feasible	Availability of Sentinel Data	More than 5-6 years cannot be produced due to unavailability of Sentinel Mission Data.	EO Data

			Update Frequency: only after snow season	Very Feasible	The characteristics of the snow cover patterns of the whole winter are needed	Results can only be produced after the snow season. The accuracy of a mid season estimate could be evaluated in regards to a post season result	Methodological
			Update Frequency: near real time	Not Feasible	The characteristics of the snow cover patterns of the whole winter are needed	Results can only be produced after the snow season. The accuracy of a mid season estimate could be evaluated in regards to a post season result	Methodological
			API access	Less Feasible	Depending on maturity of developed hosting and software tools in OEMC project.	Provide best practices and templates on how to access and process the results (e.g. aggregation to catchments). Provide predefined formats and aggregations according to the stakeholders needs.	Technical
17	Drought Monitoring at high resolution throughout Italy	CNR	Drought indices	Feasible	Definition of the indices	Testing multiple EO and model products	Methodological
			1-week latency	Feasible	Data availability (Sentinel-1)	N/A	EO Data
18	EU Flood risk maps at high resolution	CNR	Very high-resolution (10 m)	Less Feasible	EO data availability	Downscaling	EO Data
			Monthly maps	Feasible	Reference data for testing	Use of multiple data sources (national maps)	In-Situ Data

19	Global drought monitoring at high resolution	CNR	Drought indices	Feasible	Integration with other products	Testing multiple approaches	Technical
20	Meteo support for modeling of carbon sequestration tool	GILAB	Provide time series of daily values of meteorological variables (mean temperature and precipitation) in a certain location	Very Feasible	See other requirements	N/A	N/A
			Spatial precision of meteorological variables should be improved	Feasible	Lower number of observational data in some areas	Include observational data from national meteorological institutes	In-Situ Data
			To cover the 1990-present period	Feasible	Lower number of observational data for earlier years	Include observational data from different sources	EO Data
			To cover Europe or to have global spatial coverage if possible	Feasible	Data processing time	Work in parallel on multiple processing servers	Processing Infrastructure
			Reliable availability of the data	Feasible	Complex automation process	Create automated tests and error report system	Methodological
21	Meteo support tool for wildfire risk	GILAB	To provide daily min, max, mean temperature, precipitation, sea level pressure at 1 km spatial resolution	Feasible	Lower number of observational data for some variables	Include observational data from different sources	EO Data

			To cover the 1990-present period	Feasible	Lower number of observational data for earlier years	Include observational data from different sources	EO Data
			To cover Europe or to have global spatial coverage if possible	Feasible	Data processing time	Work in parallel on multiple processing servers	Processing Infrastructure
			Proper maintenance	Feasible	Complex automation process	Create automated tests and error report system	Methodological
			Easy to use data in the ML/AI models	Very Feasible	N/A	Different data formats and access	N/A
22	Meteo-based agricultural insurance tool	GILAB	Time series of the daily meteorological data for specific location	Feasible	Lower number of observational data for some variables; See other requirements	Include observational data from different sources	EO Data
			To cover the 1960-present period	Less Feasible	Lower number of observational data for earlier years	Include observational data from different sources. 1990-present is more feasible	EO Data
			To cover Europe or to have global spatial coverage if possible	Feasible	Data processing time	Work in parallel on multiple processing servers	Processing Infrastructure
			Provide high quality data	Feasible	Lower data accuracy than desired	Using state-of-the-art ML spatio-temporal interpolation methods	Methodological
			Easy to access	Very Feasible	N/A	Different data formats and access	Technical

			Implement the final solutions for the risks based on the meteorological data	Feasible	Dependency on KARAVIAS	Work with KARAVIAS	Technical
			Good maintenance	Feasible	Complex automation process	Create automated tests and error report system	Methodological
23	Air quality assessment at continental scale	IFGI	Operational use	Very Feasible	Deploying the developed workflow on the stakeholders system	Reproducible code + docker container (deployable on PC and cloud); clear documentation	Technical
			Continuity of predictor variable products	Feasible	Auxiliary data could be discontinued / inaccessible in the future	Carefully select data sources from long-term projects	EO Data
			Additional independent station reference data	Less Feasible	Most public station data already reported to EEA	Consider sensor networks from local authorities or Citizen Science data	In-Situ Data
24	Air quality assessment at regional scale	IFGI	Stakeholder is missing				
25	EU reforestation tool	OGH	European coverage	Very Feasible	Absence of predictor variables or point data	Collaborate with other partners to get data, inform the users of uncertainties	In-Situ Data
			Increase list of species/include invasive species	Less Feasible	Absence of point data (not enough observations for invasive or rare species)	Clearly define list of species of interest with the stakeholders, limit the area of interest	In-Situ Data

			Include future climatic scenarios	Very Feasible	CHELSEA shutting down!	N/A	EO Data
			Growth/success rate	Less Feasible	Objectively define success rate, predictor variables that influence it and quantify it	Stakeholder may have inside knowledge on this and their preferred definition	Methodological
26	Global topographic and hydrological service	OGH	Global ensemble model based on multisource data	Very Feasible	Already implemented	https://github.com/openlandmap/spatial-layers/tree/main/FDTM	Data Harmonisation
			Global basic morphometric parameters (slope, orientation, landform class etc)	Feasible	Large computing time / it requires really the best global DTM	Combination of GDAL, GRASS GIS, WhiteBox tools running in parallel (per tile)	Processing Infrastructure
			Global hydrological variables (catchment boundaries / area, wetness index, erosion risk...)	Less Feasible	Large computing time / is controversial hence accuracy needs to be high	Running in parallel with large tiles + overlap?	Processing Infrastructure
			Integration of data in opentopography.org and openlandmap.org	Feasible	Contacts to be made but in principle they support our work very much	N/A	Technical
27	Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales	LWE	Interview is missing				
28	Development of EU -biodiversity monitor	ETH	Spatial resolution 100m	Very Feasible	Computational limits	Downscale if necessary	Capacity Constraints

			Licensing	Very Feasible	None	N/A	N/A
			Uncertainty estimates	Feasible	Computational limits	use state of the art methodologies	Capacity Constraints
29	Development of the World-refore station monitor	ETH	The same stakeholder and requirements as for the use case 28				
30	Data cube for spatial modeling for Sinai	OGH	Sinai coverage	Very Feasible	Absence of relevant data	Create dataset ourselves	EO Data
			Coarse resolution	Very Feasible	N/A	N/A	Methodological
			30-50 years temporal extent	Feasible	Some predictor variables may have a limited temporal extent	Extrapolate predictor variables or introduce proxy variables	Methodological
			Relationship between vegetation indices and biophysical variables	Feasible	It will depend on the predictor variables chosen, some may have limited information or scientific backing	Discuss with the stakeholder main information they're interested to, create a defined list	Methodological
31	Tools for Digitalisation of Agriculture in Ethiopia	OGH	Annotation tool	Very Feasible	Skilled GIS experts to get familiar with tools and use as production	Possible local/remote training/workshop in Ethiopia	Technical
			Continuous data at local, national, regional level	Feasible	Accessibility and data hosting	Cloud-based data format and explore the possibility of local data hosting	EO Data
			Vegetation biophysical parameters	Less Feasible	Absence of point data	Collaborate with MoA to explore all possible point data	In-Situ Data

			Flood and drought monitor	Less Feasible	Local validation and data collection	Collaborate with National Disaster Risk Management Commission of Ethiopia to confirm the natural disaster	In-Situ Data
32	Tools and data for improved biomass estimation	IIASA	Differently preprocessed canopy heights	Very Feasible	No	download and custom pre-processing of satellite lidar data	Methodological
			Calibrated canopy heights	Less Feasible	Calibration data	Limiting the analysis on areas with airborne LiDAR data	EO Data
			Uncertainties for all metric	Not Feasible	Limited validation data	Uncertainty for products with validation data, or relative uncertainty among all processing algorithms	In-Situ Data
			Global coverage	Not Feasible	Cal/Val data, project time constraints	Follow-up activities/projects	EO Data
			Annual products	Not Feasible	Cal/Val. Data should match satellite data in time and space	Follow-up activities/projects	EO Data

Appendix B – Impact Assessment Table

Table 3: The extensive table with primary and secondary impact type as well as different policies related to each OEMC use case (rows). The online version of the table can be found on the following [LINK](#).

Use Case Num.	Title	Impact type	Second Impact Type	EU Policies	UN, National, or International Policies
1	Land Degradation Neutrality tool	tool & data creation	impact policy	not provided. "There is no EU-level strategy on desertification and land degradation. Rather, there is a range of strategies, action plans and spending programmes, such as the Common Agricultural Policy, the EU Forest Strategy, or the EU strategy on adaptation to climate change, which are relevant to combating desertification,"	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD): land degradation neutrality (LDN) targets
2	EU soil observatory farmer alert system	tool & data creation	data processing	European soil law, European Soil Mission, Soil Health Law. EU Soil Strategy for 2030	United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD)
3	Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tool	tool & data creation	no second impact type	EU's biodiversity strategy for 2030	CBD: NBSAPS (track biodiversity for national targets)
4	Mosquito alert system for Italy	improving data and information	data processing	National Zika monitoring policies. Regulation (EC) No 851/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 april 2004 establishing a European Centre for disease prevention and control	Regional policy for adaptation to climate change, the development of agenda 2030. WHO Zika virus monitoring policies

5	Forest management & tracking tool for Croatia	tool & data creation	impact policy	EU Habitats and Birds Directives /Natura 2000	United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests 2031. Forest Principles (UNCED)
6	Soil carbon accounting system for world mangroves	tool & data creation	impact policy	No mangroves in Europe	Global Mangrove Watch
7	EU constructions tracking system in forests	tool & data creation	impact policy	no interview. EU Forest Strategy for 2030. National level regulations that establish construction rights on forest land (Croatia example in comment) / EU Habitats and Birds Directives /Natura 2000	United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests 2031. Forest Principles (UNCED)
8	Global monitoring system for livestock and grasslands / pastures	improving data and information	impact policy	EU Nature Restoration law. EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), CAP Strategic Plans	<u>Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 15.3.1Zero-Net deforestation 2030 policies. Food security . Global Forum for Food and Agriculture. GlobalAgenda for Sustainable Livestock</u>
9	Crop yield monitoring system for Africa	tool & data creation	no second impact type	Not relevant. Stakeholders in Africa	UN STG on reducing food insecurity, land degradation neutrality. Malabo Declaration on Accelerated Agricultural Growth and Transformation for Shared Prosperity and Improved Livelihoods

10	Large-area estimation of forest carbon emissions	improving data and information	impact policy	EU climate law, Nature Restoration Law, Evolving EU forest monitoring law, EU regulation on deforestation free commodities; National and EU climate policies, as well as other policies with climate objectives	UNFCCC- NDCs
11	EU-rapid forest disturbance monitoring tool	tool & data creation	impact policy	EU Habitats and Birds Directives, Nature Restoration Law. Green deal, EU Forest Strategy for 2030. Regulation (EC) No 2152/2003 concerning monitoring of forests and environmental interactions in the Community (Forest Focus). Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe (MCPFE)	United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests 2031. Forest Principles (UNCED)
12	Tropical deforestation monitoring and characterisation tool	tool & data creation	impact policy	EU Deforestation Regulation (EUDR), EU-Mercosur Trade Agreement	National deforestation laws (in tropical countries)
13	Tool to estimate local temperatures changes following an increase in forest cover	improving data and information	tool & data creation	EU Green Deal	United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests 2031. Forest Principles (UNCED)
14	Planet health index	data processing	improving data and information	EU Green Deal, Mapping and Assessment of Ecosystems and their Services (MAES), EU Biodiversity Strategy	SDGs, Ecosystem Assessment, IPBES Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, CBD
15	SIF-based high spatial resolution GPP flux estimations	Improving stakeholder tools	no second impact type	EU climate law, National and EU climate policies, as well as other policies with climate objectives	UNFCCC- NDCs, UN REDD

16	High resolution SWE in selected mountain regions	tool & data creation	impact policy	Water Framework Directive (WFD), Floods Directive	UN-Water Integrated Monitoring Initiative for SDG 6 (IMI-SDG6), Global Water Security2023 Assessment
17	Drought Monitoring at high resolution throughout Italy	tool & data creation	impact policy	The Water Framework Directive (WFD) 2000/60/EC and the Floods Directive 2007/60/EC. Integrated Drought Management Programme in Central and Eastern Europe, National drought management plans	National Civil Protection centers across Italy. Joint Integrated Drought Management Programme of WMO and GWP
18	EU Flood risk maps at high resolution	tool & data creation	improving data and information	not provided. Floods Directive (Directive 2007/60/EC, Flood Hazard Maps and Flood Risk Maps	WMO and GWP Associated Programme on Flood Management
19	Global drought monitoring at high resolution	tool & data creation	improving data and information	Union Civil Protection Mechanism (UCPM), Water Framework Directive (WFD), Climate adaptation. Integrated Drought Management Programme in Central and Eastern Europe, National drought management plans	Joint Integrated Drought Management Programme of WMO and GWP
20	Meteo support for modeling of carbon sequestration tool	tool & data creation	no second impact type	not aware. EU Green deal, EU Climate policies	UNFCCC- NDCs
21	Meteo support tool for wildfire risk	tool & data creation	impact policy	Forest Fires Prevention: Reg. EEC 2158/92 Reg. EEC 804/94 Reg. (EC) 2152/03 Forest Monitoring and Environmental Interactions "Forest Focus"	UN Decade of Ecosystem Restoration, Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030, SDGs
22	Meteo-based agricultural insurance tool	tool & data creation	no second impact type	Agro insurance related regulations. EU Common Agricultural Policy	WTO Uruguay Round Agreement on Agriculture, Annex 2

23	Air quality assessment at continental scale	improving data and information	no second impact type	Air quality directive, Clean air for Europe (CAFE)	Not clear
24	Air quality assessment at regional scale	improving data and information	no second impact type	no interview	Not clear
25	EU reforestation tool	tool & data creation	impact policy	not provided. EU forest strategy. EU Nature Restoration Law	United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests 2031. Forest Principles (UNCED), Global Partnership on Forest Landscape Restoration (GPFLR), e Forest and Landscape Restoration Mechanism (FLRM)
26	Global topographic and hydrological service	tool & data creation	improving data and information	Agri-environmental indicator: soil erosion, logging, vegetation growth year over year, flooding area	Not clear
27	Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales	Impact policy	data processing	no interview. Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD).	UNEP Regional Seas Programme, Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans, The Global Programme of Action for the Protection of the Marine Environment from Land-based Activities.
28	Development of EU-biodiversity monitor	tool & data creation	impact policy	EU's biodiversity strategy for 2030	United Nations' Decade on Ecosystem Restoration, CBD: NBSAPS (track biodiversity for national targets)
29	Development of the World-reforestation monitor	tool & data creation	impact policy	no interview. Green deal, EU Forest Strategy for 2030. Regulation (EC) No 2152/2003 concerning monitoring of forests and environmental interactions in the Community (Forest Focus). Ministerial Conference on the Protection of Forests in Europe (MCPFE)	United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests 2031. Forest Principles (UNCED)

30	Data cube for spatial modeling for Sinai	tool & data creation	data processing	Water Framework Directive (WFD)	Not clear
31	Tools for Digitalisation of Agriculture in Ethiopia	improving data and information	tool & data creation	Not clear	National Environmental Protection Policy
32	Tools and data for improved biomass estimation	tool & data creation	improving data and information	EU Green Deal, CCI biomass protection of Native Forests legislation Legislative Law, EU biodiversity strategy for 2030	United Nations Strategic Plan for Forests 2031. Forest Principles (UNCED)

Appendix C – Data Gap Assessment Table

Table 4: The extensive table with environmental and geospatial data gaps identified per each OEMC use case from the stakeholder interviews. The online version of the table can be found on the following [LINK](#).

Use case Num.	Title	Reported environmental or geospatial data gaps
1	Land Degradation Neutrality tool	(UNCCD) SOC and LC are correlated so an alternative would significant We would like to have SOC and AGC and not just SOC Big difference between developed countries and developing countries (due to resources) Anything that would be able to estimate "land potential" (in a broader sense) would be very important X: Within the same cover types or between? Y: Everything, everywhere, all of the time; how can "productive" can this degraded land become through restoration activities
2	EU soil observatory farmer alert system	(JRC) High-res crop data are missing, data about management practice are also missing and should be more available from RS if possible, to improve the estimation-unit for statistics for smaller regions
3	Biodiversity monitoring and reporting tool	1. (Mirova) A publicly available dataset on biodiversity trends at high enough temporal and spatial resolution that can be used 2. (IDH) Existing datasets on soil are missing, specifically on soil health. (How to measure soil health?) biodiversity that relates with other indicators. At the moment there are no good biodiversity indicators or solutions that can be realistically applied by companies (lower costs, at broader ranges). not many companies seeing how biodiversity can help them in terms of providing ecosystem services they are into these topics more from consumer pressure
4	Mosquito alert system for Italy (zanzara tigre)	(Regione Emilia Romagna) The inclusion of predictor variables for forecasting with the implementation of different scenarios (i.e. precipitation, assumption and scenario-forecasting assuming temperatures only can be arranged quickly)
5	Forest management & tracking tool for Croatia	(UNDP - HR) Usage of satellite imagery (Sentinels, Landsat)
6	Soil carbon accounting system for world mangroves	(TNC) There are multiple data sources for extent, above ground biomass (e.g. https://daac.ornl.gov/CMS/guides/CMS_Global_Map_Mangrove_Canopy.html), these could be sync / harmonized or at least made available in the same data stack TNC would be happy to have one place to find all the products
7	EU constructions tracking system in forests	Interview is missing
8	Global monitoring system for livestock and grasslands / pastures	1. (WRI) Specifically regarding Global Pasture Watch there many kinds of data that could add meaning or value, including land tenure, the evolutionary history of grazing, dominant forage or forage quality, more finely resolved livestock production systems, or dominant grazing practices. It would also be valuable to combine our data with other biodiversity and ecosystem service datasets to help us determine high-value grasslands. Such datasets could provide information on habitat connectivity, or grassland, pollinator, or bird biodiversity.2. (LAPIG/UFG) The usage of Sentinel 1, 2, and 5 data can

		be increased for our pasture mapping. Nightlight, climate and other global data will be interesting to explore in our pasture mapping.
9	Crop yield monitoring system for Africa	high-res. satellite images (PlanetScope) are missing, and more analysis ready data (e.g., without gaps in Landsat time-series, cloud-free images, etc.), a service with satellite images available during field visits on a tablet or phone, with offline support. A geospatial data server to host the spatial data generated in different projects (crop-type maps, field data) is also missing.
10	Large-area estimation of forest carbon emissions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (OECD) Up-to-date biomass information at high resolution If possible, integration with national datasets Multi-date biomass estimates for carbon stock change assessments 2. (WRI) Up to date biomass information at high resolution Better integration with in-situ datasets (i.e.NFIs) Multi-date biomass estimates for carbon stock change analysis
11	EU-rapid forest disturbance monitoring tool	(JRC) collection & coordination of airborne lidar campaigns performed in EU. High quality reference data on forest disturbances across Europe to train algorithms and/or evaluate products and models with
12	Tropical deforestation monitoring and characterisation tool	(INPE) Availability of SAR L-band data.
13	Tool to estimate local temperatures changes following an increase in forest cover	(JRC) We are working on our BDAP (https://jeodpp.jrc.ec.europa.eu/bdap/) which increases the collection of EO data. Within this we are building a collection of software tools to process and "make sense" of the data within the BDAP.
14	Planet health index	(ECB) homogenised/standardised global platform that is comparable in time and space in terms of biodiversity loss and impacts of biodiversity loss in economy The problem is with biodiversity we don't have one single indicator, e.g. the cost of carbon in the economy but we have a number of products on the ecosystem services indicators. Indicators examples: mean species abundance, environmental pressures We are also interested in indicators related to water and water related risk. Most important ecosystem services: water provision and mass stabilisation with erosion control
15	SIF-based high spatial resolution GPP flux estimations	(RECCAP2/GCP) For RECCAP, data that could serve (beyond GPP) are info on changes in carbon stocks, and therefore more precisely maps of biomass and land cover/use/management change at high spatial resolution. Increasing resolution of SIF data could be useful depending on the applications.

16	High resolution SWE in selected mountain regions	(Office for Hydrology and Dams South Tyrol) Realtime measurements of e.g. soilmoisture/dwells, SWE from Fondazione CIMA for alpine region available - comparison data/validation data/quality information is missing missing data stream
17	Drought Monitoring at high resolution throughout Italy	(National Department of Civil Protection (DPC)) High-resolution data over mountainous areas are missing. The information on irrigation water use is missing in the current method for drought assessment. The data on drought impacts should be included, not only for the agricultural sector but also for drinking water and the industrial sector.
18	EU Flood risk maps at high resolution	(Descartes Underwriting) Currently, consistent and high-resolution flood hazard maps over Europe are missing.
19	Global drought monitoring at high resolution	(JRC) High-resolution data could bring added-value especially in complex terrain areas. Information on irrigation water use is not available.
20	Meteo support for modeling of carbon sequestration tool	N/A
21	Meteo support tool for wildfire risk	(ForestSat) We need as much as possible geospatial data that could be related to the forestry and forest fire risks.
22	Meteo-based agricultural insurance tool	(KARAVIAS INSURANCE BROKERS S.A.) The data related to extreme events are mostly only available locally and not at the European or global level. The availability of this kind of data, possible high quality and easy to access would be good for the agro insurance sector.

23	Air quality assessment at continental scale	(EEA Topic Center Health and Environment) Issue: reliability of data, particularly for citizen science data; potentially the hourly and daily maps mentioned above
24	Air quality assessment at regional scale	stakeholder is missing
25	EU reforestation tool	<p>(European Forest Institute (EFI)) Our role in Wageningen is to coordinate and develop a forest restoration tool to make sure that the monitoring is done in a standardised and harmonised way so that we can produce the variables that give insights.</p> <p>The forest restoration law that is being currently developed in Brussels guides the definitions of the minimum and necessary criteria for these data.</p> <p>We try to use the national forest inventory data (mostly plot data, reasonably harmonised). We use other GIS data to identify locations and other tasks</p>
26	Global topographic and hydrological service	<p>(ISG) need to be able to differentiate between what is surface vs what is terrain</p> <p>In US, discussions around every 10 years, make a global map at cm resolution to monitor changes</p> <p>Issue is ensemble modeling combining different time series; when we look at change modeling in the world, we need a defined time stamp to assess year on year, for example</p> <p>versions by time period see living planets conference session on mission to have very defined time stamps</p> <p>OEMC mission: reduce complexity for users</p>
27	Scale-dependency of "potential" marine biodiversity distribution patterns a national and European scales	Interview is missing
28	Development of EU-biodiversity monitor	(Restor) Nothing of note. If developed successfully (including optimal requirements), EU biodiversity monitor and world forest monitor would provide substantial advances on the datasets Restor hosts currently, and provide a wealth of new and relevant information to our user base. The base target product is a deforestation product but the we are developing a spectral biodiversity monitoring approach (EO). Trait-diversity product is the main to be developed. for restor the diversity would be key and currently we find it to be the missing piece of the puzzle. Now we are working based on other products (e.g. evapotranspiration) but these dont capture all aspects that we are interested in. while we have other products (e.g. greenness) we would be very interested in all kinds of diversity products from EO for various reasons.
29	Development of the World-reforestation monitor	The same stakeholder as for the use case 28

30	Data cube for spatial modeling for Sinai	(The Weather Makers) We are missing a data processing pipeline that allows us to assimilate various environmental/geospatial datasets in an efficient, effective manner to scientifically substantiate our landscape development plans. We also do not have the right data-infrastructure in place to perform the necessary analyses.
31	Tools for Digitalisation of Agriculture in Ethiopia	(MOA) The gaps are related to limited access to data sources and inadequate capacity on the use of earth monitoring tools; areas of interest include: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Reduction in soil loss/land degradation/erosion risk<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Land use land cover change- Change in biomass (woody and non-woody)- Improvement in biodiversity geospatial data with high resolution is missing (AAU) Land us land cover, vegetation cover, carbon sequestration, land management practices, etc (GIZ)
32	Tools and data for improved biomass estimation	1. (GAMMA Remote Sensing AG) tailored and calibrated satellite LiDAR data for biomass estimation 2. (Embrapa) data on species identification is lacking, high-resolution (<3m) remote sensing data